

INDIAN MILITARY FAMILY ASSOCIATION

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ABSTRACT

The IMFA (Indian Military Family Association) is a web application and an Android application mainly for the people/users who wants to help by donating funds to the family of military soldiers died in service. In this application user will gets to know about the current news regarding the soldiers who gives their life in service for India. We are providing details of family of the soldiers to which the fund will be donated. The donated fund will be delivered in the account of soldier's family member either parents / spouses / children's directly. The amount of any number you can donate even a small amount can also be donated. The various donate option is also provided like Demand Draft & Credit Card Donation and mode of payment like paytm. You can use these option as per your ease.